

Sea of Gluons and Quarks Confinement Visualization– 8 Theory

O Manor

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the 8T alongside the recent theoretical advancements in the subject of bosons to be net curvature on the Einstein metric tensor, which is supported by the coupling constants series – analysis of the sea of gluons can be made. The key point is that each gluon is a curvature causing other curvature to converge to its position. The result is a cluster of gluons concentrated at a certain domain, and can be visualized as an hyperbole excluding the option of escape, and so link it to quark confinement.

Introduction

The new 8T framework regard fermions and in particular quarks as arbitrary variations of a manifold which vanish into matter. The process of vanishing ensuring that no curvature is allowed. The exclusion of curvature yielding than the group suggested by Gell-Mann in the 20-th century. That is described by the main equation that describes a varying Lorentz manifold, which was invoked stationary:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Allowing it to experience arbitrary amounts of curvature, we have proven the existence of Quarks:

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

That was by discretizing and partitioning the arbitrary variation term in (1.1), and by proving the series must have only two distinct elements which differ in sign and vanish to zero. By allowing the elements to vary, we proven they form threefold combinations.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$\delta g_1(0)\delta g_2(Y)\delta g_1$$

Since, we have a threefold combination that will pair the inverse in sign; so the both would vanish into zero. Thus, we can consider the total charge of the threefold combination to be an integer and its inverse:

$$\delta g_1(0)\delta g_2(Y)\delta g_1 \Leftrightarrow \delta g_2(0)\delta g_1(Y)\delta g_2$$

Since each gluon increase the probability of arrival of other gluons, as it is a net curvature on the matrix tensor, and by that reasoning gluons will pull other gluons to their position in agreement with the "sea of gluons" we can visualize how the Quark gluon configuration looks like.

From that visualization it is clear that the quarks cannot escape the threefold combination, making one of the quarks escape is synonymous with rolling it uphill along an immensely curved hyperbole, each boson is contributing to the positive summation of curvature. (1.33) and (1.34) for example describe the photon emitted from an electron, as it was proven by the coupling constants series (1.35), which is isomorphic to prime numbers or one.

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \tag{1.33}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \tag{1.34}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 \dots \quad (1.35)$$

Using the new framework of the 8T, it is than possible to imagine quark confinement in a very simple and elegant way. The quark confinement is an embodiment of the large set of gluons present in the threefold combination, causing the matric tensor to be curved. The metric tensor is co curved that the only way to consider separation of those threefold would be to eliminate the gluons, such elimination seems impossible. Suppose you eliminate one gluon, the rest of gluons by that time may already added an additional gluons and so the number will be invariant, in agreement with quark confinement.

References

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- [2] O. Manor. "Curvature and Probability of Arrival" In: (2021)
- [3] O. Manor. "8T: Sea of Gluons" In: (2021)